

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN PROTECTING TEENAGERS FROM THE IMPACT OF THE VIRTUAL WORLD

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the topic of the role of foreign experience in protecting adolescents from the influence of the virtual world. Also in the content of the article is the concept of the virtual world, Internet addiction, adolescence and its characteristics, tools of the virtual world, man-made methods of influencing human consciousness, skills of working with youth. information, the analysis of scientific concepts and approaches to dependence on the virtual world is also covered in detail.

Key words: virtual world, Internet addiction, adolescence, information, man-made factors, information protection, vulnerability, human, built environment, mideaworld, values, goals, computer, sites.

РОЛЬ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В ЗАЩИТЕ ПОДРОСТКОВ ОТ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ВИРТУАЛЬНОГО МИРА

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена теме роли зарубежного опыта в защите подростков от влияния виртуального мира. Также в содержании статьи понятие виртуального мира, интернет-зависимость, подростковый возраст и его характеристики, инструменты виртуального мира, техногенные методы воздействия на сознание человека, навыки работы с молодежью. информации, также подробно освещен анализ научных концепций и подходов к зависимости от виртуального мира.

Ключевые слова: виртуальный мир, интернет-зависимость, подростковый возраст, информация, техногенные факторы, защита от информации, уязвимость, человек, искусственная среда, мидеамир, ценности, цели, компьютер, сайты.

Introduction. It is known that although the protection of adolescents from the influence of the virtual world is widely studied by many specialists in this field, including psychologists, educators, sociologists and philosophical researchers, this issue is still considered the main goal of interdisciplinary research. Because most of the studies conducted were conducted in control groups, which many researchers objected to, that is, control groups were not considered sufficient objects to solve this problem. In addition, this issue cannot be fully studied only through surveys or interviews. Psychologist ON. Arestova said that in order to scientifically substantiate whether

a person has a low or high level of dependence on the virtual environment, it is advisable to repeat the study of subjects in large laboratories.

Therefore, the identification of the problem of virtual protection of adolescents is determined not only by tests, but also by laboratory examination, reflecting some practical actions.

B.A. Burova in her scientific article entitled "Mechanisms of Internet addiction" explains the problem as follows: "Before conducting research on the issue of Internet addiction, the researcher must first observe with his own eyes the activities of individuals with this behavior.

Because many psychological factors are determined leading to this method. For example, the game, the Internet, time, age, social status, etc. According to these views, the impact of the virtual world can be determined not only by psychodiagnostic means, but also by observation. The issue of the influence of the virtual world was also widely studied by A.E. Voyskunsky, and the author suggests specific directions for studying the problem. According to the author, these directions should include:

- An approach aimed at studying changes in the activities of individuals in a virtual environment;
- An approach aimed at a separate study of the factors causing Internet addiction and the stages of its development;
- An approach aimed at developing a model of dependence on the virtual environment;
- Dependence on the virtual environment and its other aspects are aimed at training, pedagogical, sociological, legal, etc. In fact, Internet addiction is not only a psychological problem, it is very important to study it on a large scale, that is, in a complex of studies.

Literature review. The problem of the risk of virtual networks is not only a question of scientific psychology, but also a strategic issue for the entire society and the state. In this issue, among the researchers A.A. Rean, I.S. Against. A.E. Voiskunsky, V.A. Loskutova, L.O. Perezhogin, A.Yu. Egorov, H.D.I. Bochkareva, A.E. Zhichkina, L.G. Leonova, N.A. Nosov, Yu.V. Fomicheva, A.F. Shaidullina, S.A. Such scientists as Shapkin, I. Shevchenko, A.G. Shmelev, Yu.D. Babaeva, T.N. Dudko, K.E. Yurenkov published unique scientific books and monographs. Among other things, according to A.V. Benediktova, the concept of addiction to the virtual environment should not be considered as pathological behavior, that is, frequent use of the Internet enriches a person. According to A.A. Chernova, cyber addiction is a complex process, and a specialist studying it should be aware of not only the achievements of psychology, but also computer technologies. Thanks to these factors, one can learn more about the influence of Internet information on a person's personality. Because most cybernetic data is monetization or business data.

Research Methodology. In general, as a theoretical and methodological basis of our study, in foreign psychology Internet addiction and its consequences, psychoprophylaxis of Internet addiction elimination, information environment and youth, information attacks and its modern manifestations, virtual world and its perception, teenagers computer skills N.A. Shapira, H.J. Shaffer, N.S. Endler, J.D. Parker, O.Yu. Yokoyama, T.N. Neverie, G. Gigerenzer, R.O. Anker, J.L.B. Rech, D.S. Weiss, K.R. Marble, T.J. Metzler, The advanced ideas of H.M. Ronfeldt were taken as a basis. A special place among psychological studies of the virtual world and the reasons for the impact on it is occupied by the studies of B.A. Barabanshchikova. The author says that addiction to the virtual environment is often observed in young children, as a result of which the process of self-awareness is disrupted. Children exposed to network information often develop the characteristic of self-esteem "I am above". Or applying lipstick to the virtual world will end with an overestimation of time. V. V. Selivanov and L. N. Selivanova, among others, conducted a study of the psychological problems of using a virtual network, in which the authors highlight the following reasons. According to the authors, unlike others, subjects of the virtual environment are characterized by aggressiveness, hostility and cynicism. They are also often distinguished as people who live with a feeling of disappointment or severe anxiety. Also, A. V. Zakhrapina, having conducted a study of the psychological factors of Internet addiction in adolescents, developed a unique proposal to solve the problem. That is, according to the scientist, the only way to prevent addiction to the virtual environment is to create a national committee to control it. This committee implements measures aimed at eliminating addiction, developing legal documents and preventive programs. The essence of this proposal is that addiction to the virtual network is not only a science, but also an organization that controls it and prevents data.

Analysis and results. It is known that the virtual world opens up a lot of opportunities for a person. Anonymity on the Internet, access from different parts of the world, communication with any user (regardless of gender, age, nationality, religion), self-realization, lack of moral rules in life on the Internet, avoidance of responsibility increase the above. mentioned risks. The virtual world manipulates people. According to experts, in the virtual world, a person's time perception system is disrupted, social activity decreases. The worst thing is that in this process the negative impact of virtual tools is not limited to spiritual and moral decline, but also causes many diseases.

From this point of view, the research work we are studying is considered one of the most relevant and topical topics, given today's difficult conditions. Therefore, as an object of research, we chose district teenagers living in cities and villages, which form the basis of the Internet flow.

In the above part of the study, we got acquainted with their average results. Now let's try to determine the significant and insignificant scales of questionnaires according to the criteria of

factor analysis. The following table presents the results of rural adolescents of the Navoi region (table 1).

Table 1

Factorization of questionnaires on protection from the virtual world

Scales	Factors	
	1	2
Internet and computer addiction		0,586
Addiction to computer games		0,768
TV addiction	0,589	
Addiction to destructive religious information		0,557
General tendency to addiction		0,624
Constructive reception of information on the Internet	0,507	
Perception of time	0,556	
Understanding the positive features of the Internet		0,529
Understand the negative sides of the Internet	0,625	
Understanding information on the Internet		0,523
Resilience	0,775	
Smart move		0,604
Overcoming reality	0,721	
Change yourself	0,635	
Positive thinking		0,713
Control of emotions		0,683

The obtained results of the study showed the following results: the main factors determining the socio-psychological mechanisms of protection of rural adolescents from the influence of the virtual world in the Navoi region (Table1). The accents included in the first factor: dependence on television, constructive perception of information on the Internet, perception of time, awareness of the negative features of the Internet, persistence, overcoming reality and self-change of scales. We conditionally called this factor (according to the considerations included in the factor): self-control on the Internet. The following considerations were taken from the second factor: addiction to the Internet and computer, addiction to computer games, addiction to destructive religious information, general tendency to addiction, awareness of the positive features of the Internet, understanding of information on the Internet, rational action, positive thinking and control of emotions. In order to prevent the risk of information and psychological safety of teenagers on the Internet, it is necessary to continue and intensify scientific research on this issue, as well as to develop programs for the formation and development of students' skills for safe behavior on the Internet, the personal sphere of children and teenagers, it is necessary to develop and implement programs for the psychological correction of the disorder.

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